

REVIEW: QING MU CHUAN 'GREENWOOD RIVERSIDE' BY YE GUANGQIN

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Ye Guangqin 叶广岑. 2007. *Qing mu chuan* 青木川 [*Greenwood Riverside*]. Xi'an 西安: Taibai wen yi chu ban she 太白文艺出版社 [Shaanxi Taibai Literature & Art Publishing House]. 301pp. ISBN 978-7-80680-467-4 (paperback 28RMB).

Ye Guangqin (Gao Minna, Du Lixia, and Liu Danling, translators). 2012. *Greenwood Riverside*. New York: Prunus Press USA, vols 1&2. 617pp. ISBN 978-1-61612-062-7 (paperback 36USD).

Born in 1948 in Beijing of the Manchu Yehe Nara Clan, related to the Empress Dowager Cixi,² and her parents' thirteenth child,³ Ye Guangqin is a novelist, essayist, and translator with a journalism degree from Renmin University. Now living in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, she also studied at Japan's Chiba University.⁴ Much of Ye's fiction is set in Beijing. The historical novels *Qianqing Men Nei 'Inside the Gate of Heavenly Purity'* (1986) and *Zhuangyuan Mei 'The Imperial Matchmaker'* (2012) narrate and romanticize historical events in feudalist Qing Dynasty society. *Cai Sang Zi 'Picking Mulberries'* (2009) and *Quan Jia Fu 'A Family Portrait'* (2015) portray the realities of Manchu modern life in Beijing. Her autobiography, *Mei You Ri Ji De Luo Fu He 'No Diary for the Luo'ao River'* (1998), won her the Fifth Junma Award.⁵

Her novel *Qing Mu Chuan* (translated into English as *Greenwood Riverside*) is set in Shaanxi Province, where Ye spent her twenties and thirties as a factory worker, nurse, and journalist. Initially published in 2007 by the Taibai Literature and Art Publishing House, the novel has attracted considerable commentary. By 22 March 2021, fifty-five papers related to the novel had been published as listed on the Wanfang Database⁶ and twenty-five papers on CNKI (Chinese National Knowledge Internet). These papers deal with comparative study, the TV adaptation, narrative techniques, characterization, and influence on local tourism.

Having recently visited Qing Mu Chuan 'Greenwood Riverside', I read Ye's novel, and, finding no English language reviews, I offer these reflections.

In contrast to Beijing, where many of her novels are set, Shaanxi is a place of bitterness and personal growth for Ye. During the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976), Ye was deprived of her office job and banished to western Shaanxi Province. At that time, her ill mother was bedridden and passed

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² <https://paper-republic.org/works/hou-zhao-lou/>, accessed 7 April 2021.

³ https://www.goodreads.com/author/show/7774950.Guangqin_Ye, accessed 14 April 2021.

⁴ <https://paper-republic.org/pers/ye-guangqin/>, accessed 25 March 2021.

⁵ "...the Junma Award (or Courser Award) [is], a national level award specially designed for outstanding cultural arts programs reflecting the life of ethnic minorities in China in the categories of TV broadcasting, movie-making and literature writing..." (http://en.chinagate.cn/reports/2006-10/10/content_2448941.htm, accessed 7 April 2021).

⁶ An authoritative Chinese academic paper database.

away soon after their separation. Taking consolation in the words of Cong Weixi, "Only after a full round of persecution and mocking shall life and destiny bestow upon you the talent of literature creation" (Li 2014:100, my translation), Ye drew literary inspiration from the sorrows she experienced.

Ye comments on Xi'an, an ancient city with a rich cultural heritage, "Every tile I came across belonged to the ancient dynasties and every step I took here was on the territory of ancient China" (Li 2014:101, my translation). Xi'an's cultural influence has also affected well-known writers such as Jia Pingwa and Chen Zhongshi. Ye's experience of life's ups and downs in Shaanxi provided a rich resource for *Greenwood Riverside* (2007) and *Lao Xian Cheng 'Old Town'* (2010), both of which helped cement her reputation as a novelist.

Qing Mu Chuan 'Greenwood Riverside' was once inhabited by the Qiang ethnic group. Known as Yong Ning Li in the Ming Dynasty (1368-1644), it was renamed No. 18 West Road Ning Qiang 'Peaceful Qiang' Prefecture in the Qing Dynasty (1636-1912). After the founding of New China in 1949, it became Qing Mu Chuan, named after the greenwood tree by the bridgehead. Reputed to be more than 1,000 years old, the tree's enormous lush green canopy of branches and leaves shaded a large area, and its circumference was claimed to be so wide that six people holding hands were unable to encircle it (Ye 2012:196).

Ye Guangqin's relationship with Qing Mu Chuan traces back to the 1980s when she worked for the *Shaanxi Worker's Daily*. While conducting interviews at a copper mine in Yangping Pass, she heard stories of a Robin-Hood-like local hero, Wei Futang. Intrigued, she visited Qing Mu Chuan in 2002 with her editor, Han Jihong, a trip described in the first chapter of her novel, *Old Town*. A second trip provided more material and led to *Qing Mu Chuan*, a novel mainly about the protagonist, Wei Futang, that unfolds from the perspectives of three narrators - Feng Ming; Feng's daughter, Feng Xiaoyu; and Zhong Yishan, a scholar and Feng's boyfriend.

Feng Ming is a former Communist Party member, a retired government official who spent his youth in Qing Mu Chuan, had a lover who died in battle and was buried there and was in charge of the escort that took Wei Futang to his execution. Motivated by nostalgia and wanting to visit his lover's grave, he travels to Qing Mu Chuan with his daughter and prospective son-in-law.

After Feng Xiaoyu, Feng's daughter, visits the local museum, she becomes curious about a missing woman, Cheng Lixue. Her inquiries provide readers with another thread in the story. Meanwhile, Zhong Yishan, a scholar and Feng's boyfriend, engages in historical research and archeological excavations, presenting history and local stories from a more objective perspective than the local seniors' oral recollections.

These three characters trudge over hills and through rivers to reach Qing Mu Chuan, located in the interior of the Qinling Mountains and straddling Shaanxi, Sichuan, and Gansu provinces.

In 1952, the protagonist, Wei Futang, received a death sentence. In the novel, his life is reviewed in flashbacks. Readers learn that Wei was born into a poor peasant family in 1902 in the final years of the declining Qing Dynasty when bandits and gamblers were in Qing Mu Chuan. Lacking wealth and power, the young Wei changes his fate by marrying a rich family's bedridden daughter, Liu Erquan. Using his father-in-law's resources, he enters the cooking oil business, accumulates power, and kills the Regional Civil Corps' head, Wei Wenbing, who bullies locals.

In the following years, Wei flees to Guangyuan, Sichuan Province, where he meets and follows the notorious bandit, Wang Sanchun, who appoints Wei as the Iron Blood Battalion leader. Under Wang's order, a member of the Battalion kills a peasant woman. Though Wei and Wang part ways soon after collusion in banditry, Wei is eventually charged with the peasant woman's death, leading to the death penalty.

After returning to Qing Mu Chuan from Guangyuan, Wei Futang finds that his wife, Liu Erquan, has died. Inheriting a large fortune, he gains power and becomes the commander-in-chief of the local military force in response to the Nationalist government's encouragement of local self-

governance. From the mid-1930s to 1952, Wei has five concubines and fathers two sons and one daughter. He organizes an army of farmers who, while plowing their own fields, are ready to serve him whenever he summons them. Wielding political and economic power, "Emperor Wei" (of this small town) establishes a regional management system. He helps fellow villagers acquire wealth by selling and trading opium to the outside world while prohibiting locals from using opium.

A legend, Wei Futang is depicted as both an outlaw villain in the chaotic world outside Qing Mu Chuan in the Republic of China period and, at the same time, a moral humanitarian bringing benefits to the locals and substantially contributing to his hometown by funding the construction of buildings and renovating the local streets and bridges. He was also respected for his devotion to education, exemplified by an inscription on his tombstone written by his daughter:

My father started Futang Middle School,¹ recruited a preeminent principal and many well-known teachers, and enrolled children to cultivate their talents. His dedication and belief in the importance of education have inspired generations. For two decades, my father devoted himself to developing Greenwood Riverside into a unique, cultured and educated community (Ye 2012:614).

The latter part of the story, narrated by Feng Xiaoyu, centers on learning the identity of the mysterious Cheng Lixue, who went missing after she came to Qing Mu Chuan with her husband, Huo Dacheng, a corrupt Guomindang official and the superintendent of education. Ambushed by Wei's band (led by his nephew, Li Shumin, in the hope of getting money), Huo abandons Cheng and flees. Afterward, Cheng Lixue appears periodically in this town but is invisible most of the time. Feng Xiaoyu suspects that Cheng was, in fact, Wei Futang's sixth concubine, Xie Miaozi. However, villagers do not divulge information about this, nor do they explain how Futang Middle School's late head, Xie Jingyi, died. As the novel notes, "Men tend to forget, sometimes deliberately" (Ye 2012:226).

Driven by curiosity, Feng Xiaoyu visits Xie Miaozi and demystifies the case. Liu Fang, Li Shumin's wife, was formerly named Cheng Fang, the younger sister of Cheng Lixue, who, in actuality, is Xie Jingyi. Despondent over her husband abandoning her during the ambush, Cheng Lixue resolves to stay in Greenwood Riverside and begin life anew with a new identity, as Xie Jingyi. With her language abilities, she teaches English at Futang Middle School and later becomes the school leader. Cheng Fang, her younger sister (a Nationalist Party member), comes to Qing Mu Chuan seeking her help. It is here that she meets and marries Li Shumin.

Later, Cheng Fang is killed in a battle between Nationalist and Communist Party soldiers. In 1952, her husband, Li, is captured and sentenced to death with his uncle, Wei Futang.

Wei Futang, trusting and supporting Communist Party governance, handed in his weapons and dismissed his troops, hoping to receive amnesty. However, fate took a different turn. He was accused of six murders and sentenced to death. On the way to his execution, Wei Futang passes by Feng Yu 'Wind and Rain' Bridge that he had sponsored. He is shot dead in the yard of Futang Middle School.

Thirty years later, in 1982, the case of Wei Futang was retried, with the result that he was posthumously rehabilitated and dubbed "Enlightened Gentry" to redefine and affirm his historical significance.

With no chronological approach, the stories and anecdotes are fragmented and strung together by senior villagers' disordered recollections of various personalities at disjointed times. The author uses this technique to present the turmoil and turbulence during this period of Chinese history.

¹ See <https://mi.mbd.baidu.com/r/l4CUi36n7O?f=cp&u=b624e66875fd6ecb> (accessed 17 April 2021) for a photograph. The school is now named Furen Middle School.

Readers are prompted to rethink the meaning of "history." Is it excavated subterranean evidence? Is it remembered and retold by people in the past?

This novel vividly portrays unique personalities. Wei Futang, the main character, moves upward socially, from a grass-root tramp to a sophisticated man of manners. He begins this steep social climb by marrying the wealthy but incapacitated Liu Erquan and cruelly acts to hasten her death, inviting cronies to his home where he treats them to feasts, thereby disturbing his wife, whom he never loved nor touched. After the death of Liu and her father, Wei inherits the family wealth. Vile as he is, he begins to change after meeting Cheng Lixue, an outstanding literate, cultured female intellectual.

Aspiring to a more sophisticated life, Wei builds Futang Middle School and encourages local children to study there. Exceptional students are sent to study at famous universities, including Sichuan University and Chongqing University, on full scholarships.

Wei's change reflects Chinese society's transformation from feudal barbarism to modern civilization characterized by the Republic of China. This era was one of turbulence and transformation where a semi-colonial, semi-feudal society ended, and a series of revolutions led to the establishment of the People's Republic of China. Evidence of modernity periodically appears throughout the novel, such as a Ford automobile, a piano Wei Futang bought, and a priest's phone that startles Wei when he and his followers attack the church. These things open his eyes and mind to modern Western technology, bringing a realization of irreversible trends. He decides to invest in education and to empower the younger generation. For example, when he breaks into the church and tries to rob the priest, he finds the latter uses a phone that "magically" notifies the police to come to apprehend them. Despite the shame and failure from this episode, he remains amazed by this small magic box - a phone.

Female characters are depicted with a touch of mystery. Cheng Lixue is the essential thread throughout the novel. Wei Futang's first glimpse of Cheng Lixue is romantic and mysterious:

When Wei Futang passed the woman he suddenly lifted his head and leaned to one side to look deeply into her eyes. They were soft and calm with no sign of anger, timidity or sadness. The woman's dark hair was set off by the blue sky and white clouds. She was the last vision of beauty Wei Futang would ever see in this lifetime (Ye 2012:186).

However, her real identity as head of the school is not unveiled until the story's end, prolonging the suspense and tantalizing readers.

Two of Wei's concubines are sisters and represent the declining feudal system. As was the case with Liu Erquan, Wei married the two Zhao sisters for material gain and because they were his equal in terms of social status. The elder sister, a Buddhist convert, calls herself "Dragon Lady" of the Buddhist Goddess of Mercy, Guan Yin. The younger one is depicted clad in a long black robe, never displaying any facial expressions.

Most of the female characters are not evildoers. Though from different family backgrounds and social statuses, they are depicted as optimistic. Some, Liu Erquan and the Zhao sisters, for example, represent the decline of the 'old' wealth families, while others, like Zhu Meiren and Cheng Lixue, are more rebellious and modern.

The influence of Occidental culture is also evident. Principal Xie Jingyi teaches English. Xie Miaozi, one of Wei's concubines, was a nun named Emily and served in a church before marriage. To some extent, these characters epitomize Wei Futang's longing for advanced Western civilization.

A beautiful artist and opera singer, Zhu Meiren, is memorably portrayed in two pages. Meiren suggests "Beauty," and Wei falls in love with her when she performs traditional Chinese drama in Huayang County, Hanzhong, Shaanxi. Wei saves her from a local rich man who wants to buy her the moment he sees her perform. Meiren, as another of Wei Futang's concubines, accompanies him and

trains as a woman warrior with a pistol in each hand. She also helps establish strict rules for Wei and his troops, clearly distinguishing praise and punishment. "Killing the rich and aiding the poor" and "doing God's work" are guidelines. Any wrongdoing, such as attacking pedestrians, women, seniors, or children, is severely punished while assaulting officials, whether good or bad, is permissible under the prevailing Robin Hood mentality - rob the rich and help the poor. Corrupt officials are killed immediately, and all their property is confiscated. Only one ear is cut off, and only half of their fortune is taken if they are found to be upright and honest. Meiren also institutes fair rules for the distribution of confiscated property. Her strong sense of community and management skills helps Wei Futang establish integrity and justice among his followers and consolidate his position for two decades.

Later, Zhu Meiren is abducted by Wang Sanchun and executed after two years of imprisonment.

Niu Yuqiu¹ comments that the novel's use of suspense, including revealing Wei Futang's destiny and the mysterious identity of Xie Jingyi, is remarkable. Suspense attracts readers, and Ye employs this device masterfully. Peng Xueming² writes:

Ye Guangqin's respect and compassion for ordinary people, historical inquiry, and interpretation of culture give her works stature and depth, as well as better poetic and historical character. Her tolerance and benevolent attitude toward humanity and history also display the literary mind and broad-mindedness of a great writer. It can be said that *Greenwood Riverside* is Ye Guangqin's masterpiece in the depths of time representing her own heart which, despite hidden wounds and pains, beats tenaciously.

The author confides, "History is not man's will. We cannot restrain passing waves, no matter how beautiful they are."³

The English translation of the novel was published in 2012 by Prunus Press USA. Professors Gao Minna, Du Lixia, and Liu Daling, the translators, are members of the Shaanxi Translators Association.⁴ Thanks to the translators and editor, the English version achieves the same effect. For example, early in the story, a paragraph describes Wei Futang's death:

He was shot to death as the oilseed canola flowers and buds were blooming vigorously, spreading their bright, brassy yellow glow with the slight odor of honey over and through the mountains. The bees were buzzing and dancing in the soft, shimmering morning sunshine. It was the time when local farmers were busy dividing the fields and property; a time when they finally stood up and seized liberation; a time when they were filled with elation and exaltation (Ye 2012:450).

Precise, well-written translation offers readers a well-composed image. Spring's fecundity serves as a foil for the death of this legendary man who brought both wealth and notoriety to a small, obscure rural community.

Some minor characters are also vividly portrayed, e.g., the bandit Wang Sanchun's savage cruelty is vividly translated:

...would then cut open the victim's chest and kick him in the back. By doing this, the person's heart would fall out of his chest. Wang Third Spring had acquired this extraordinary skill as a result of having practiced

¹ <http://www.chinawriter.com.cn/bk/2009-07-25/36985.html>, accessed 26 March 2021 (my translation).

² <http://www.chinawriter.com.cn/bk/2009-07-25/36985.html>, accessed 26 March 2021 (my translation).

³ Ibid, accessed 26 March 2021 (my translation).

⁴ Copyedited by the American writer, Jerry Piasecki, whose works include *Harry and Lucy* (2010) and *They're Torturing Teachers in Room 104* (1997).

on numerous victims. The heart kicked out in this way would be sliced raw to go with his alcohol. But if the heart was too fatty, it would be pan-fried (Ye 2012:142).

One issue of contention is the translation of Chinese names. Often the result of a local tradition of naming with references to nature or within the hierarchy and seniority of kinship groups, the Chinese names are literal English translations rather than Pinyin. For example, Wang Sanchun, in the above passage, is rendered "Wang Third Spring," with "spring" indicating season rather than "spring water." Liu Erquan, Wei's wife, the second daughter of her family, translates as "Second Spring" or "Two Springs." "Spring" might also refer to "spring water," suggesting "source of life." However, in the English version, Liu Erquan is translated as "Liu Second Spring," which lacks foreignization¹ and is an excess of domestication translation² and loses the original Chinese cultural flavor. Other examples include Zhu Meiren translated as Beauty Zhu, Lao Wan as Old Wan, and Liu Xiaozhu as Liu Piglet.

These examples indicate failure to render the names of the Chinese characters into English faithfully. Transliteration and annotations added in brackets are recommended in authoritative translations of Chinese classics such as *Hong Lou Meng 'A Dream of Red Mansions'* that uses Pinyin to render names instead of providing only English.

Cultural equivalence is also evident in the English version, to cater to an English readership. For example, an idiom about revenge is translated as, "Revenge is a dish best served cold" (Ye 2012:450). The Chinese version is: "Even ten years is not too late for a gentleman to have his revenge."

In 2014 this novel was also adapted for a forty-four-episode TV series and broadcast as *Yi Dai Xiao Xiong 'A Hero'*. The A-list Chinese cast included Sun Honglei and Chen Shu. As at 24 March 2021, it had been accessed 3.4 million times on Bilibili³. Douban⁴ rated it 7/10. In the TV adaptation, the story develops chronologically, and third-person narration and flashbacks are not included. Certain characters in the novel are also absent. Other changes include presenting Wei Futang as He Futang. The opera singer Zhu Cailing, whose archetype was Zhu Meiren, was given a lot of screen time and is depicted divorcing He Futang and joining the Communist Party. He Futang, instead of being sentenced to death, becomes a school teacher and leads a peaceful life. Wei's personal heroic charisma is stressed less than in the novel, while the theme "hero of the times" is emphasized.

The romance between Wei Futang and Cheng Lixue was a selling point of the TV series. For better or worse, this TV series further popularized Wei Futang, bringing notoriety to the once sleepy ancient town of Qing Mu Chuan, which is now on the National List of Protected Traditional Villages in China. The Qing Mu Chuan Administrative Office of the Ning Qiang County Management Committee manages what has become a tourist attraction. An eight-hour drive from Xi'an City, or a one-hour train from Guangyuan City, plus a twenty-minute ride in a tutu car brings the visitor to the two-street small town surrounded by mountains. Hui Long Chang 'Winding Dragon Street' stretches along Jinxi 'Gold Stream', a name from the time gold was extracted locally and exported beyond the mountains.

¹ "Foreignization ... constructs a certain image of the foreign that is informed by the receiving situation but aims to question it by drawing on materials that are not currently dominant, namely the marginal and the nonstandard, the residual and the emergent" (Venuti 2008:19-20).

² "Domestication is the strategy of making a text closely conform to the culture of the language being translated to, which may involve the loss of information from the source text so as to focus on the target audience. This happens primarily when a certain situation does not exist in the target culture" (<https://bit.ly/3xvTlm9>, accessed 29 April 2021).

³ Based in Shanghai, Bilibili is a Chinese video sharing website.

⁴ "Douban is a hybrid of interest-based social networking platforms [and] has become the preferred online social network for scholars, academics and writers in China" (<https://tinyurl.com/229b847x>, accessed 27 March 2021).

Old buildings with notable architectural features built by Wei Futang and others during the Republic of China stand along both sides of the stone-slab paved Winding Dragon Street. Among these buildings are the Opium House, the bank, a boat-shaped hotel, and other typical southern Shaanxi style wooden-plank buildings. Shops open onto the stone pavement. Courtyards and living rooms are inside. The Wei Family Manor is a must-visit with its architectural style conveying the culture of Wei's times as well as the stories of its former inhabitants.

A token greenwood tree stands silent and proud by the Wei Family manor, witness to the passage of time. Wei Futang's son sits in a room in a building facing the street, ready to autograph copies of *Qing Mu Chuan*.

Another table with copies of this novel stands on the threshold of Zhongde Shu Wu, an antique bookstore, named after its owner, Xu Zhongde, a former Futang Middle School student and one of the first batch of students financially supported by Wei Futang for post-graduate study in Sichuan University in Chengdu. Upon his return, Xu Zhongde became Wei Futang's chief of staff. Xu and other senior elders were oral history sources in *Qing Mu Chuan* who gave Ye Guangqin first-hand accounts for her creations. Xu, an important character, is fictionalized in this novel. The three narrators visit Xu, who tells the stories in which he played a role. Ye describes her interview experience with the real-life Mr. Xu and his family in the novel's epilogue, adding historical authenticity. (This part is omitted in the English version of *Greenwood Riverside*.)

On the hill behind the street, Furen Middle School remains open, providing local children compulsory nine-grade education. Wei Futang's tomb¹ is on the opposite hillside.

Qing Mu Chuan (22 October 2020, Wu Jing).

¹ See <https://me.mbd.baidu.com/r/l4CyldgNJC?f=cp&u=129f9f4ba0ce12cc> (accessed 17 April 2021) for a photograph of the tombstone.

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CHINESE TERMS

Beijing 北京	Furen Middle School, Furen Zhong Xue 辅仁中学
Bilibili 哔哩哔哩	
Cai Sang Zi 采桑子	Futang Middle School, Futang Zhong Xue 辅唐中学
Chen Shu 陈数	
Chen Zhongshi 陈忠实	Gao Minna 高敏娜
Cheng Fang 程芳	Guan Yin 观音
Cheng Lixue 程立雪	Guangyuan 广元
Chengdu 成都	Guomindang 国民党, Guomintang, Kuomintang
Chongqing 重庆	Han Jihong 韩霁虹
Cixi 慈禧	Hanzhong 汉中 City
Cong Weixi 从维熙	He Futang 何辅堂
Douban 豆瓣	Hong Lou Meng 红楼梦
Du Lixia 杜丽霞	Huayang 华阳 County
Feng Ming 冯明	Hui Long Chang 回龙场
Feng Xiaoyu 冯小雨	Huo Dacheng 霍大成
Feng Yu Bridge, Feng Yu Qiao 风雨桥	

- Jia Pingwa 贾平凹
 Jinxi 金溪
 Junma 骏马
 Lao Wan 老万
 Li Shumin 李树敏
 Liu Danling 刘丹翎
 Liu Erquan 刘二泉
 Liu Xiaozhu 刘小猪
 Ma Xiuhua 马秀华
Mei You Ri Ji De Luo Fu He 没有日记的罗敷河
 Ming 明 Dynasty
 Ning Qiang 宁强
 Niu Yuqiu 牛玉秋
 Peng Xueming 彭学明
 Pinyin 拼音
 Qi Jiahua 祁嘉华
 Qiang 羌
Qianqing Men Nei 乾清门内
 Qing 清 Dynasty
 Qing Mu Chuan 青木川
 Qing Mu Chuan Ancient Town, Qing mu chuan
 gu zhen jing qu guan wei hui 青木川古镇景
 区管委会
 Qinling 秦岭 Mountains
Quan Jia Fu 全家福
 Renmin 人民 University
 Shaanxi 陕西 Province
 Shaanxi Normal University, Shaanxi shi fan da
 xue 陕西师范大学
*Shaanxi Worker's Daily, Shaanxi gong ren
 bao* 陕西工人报
 Shang Yaning 尚亚宁
 Shanghai 上海 City
 Sichuan 四川 Province
 Sun Honglei 孙红雷
 Wang Sanchun 王三春
 Wei Futang 魏辅唐 (historical person); 魏富堂
 (fictional character)
 Wei Wenbing 魏文炳
 Wu Jing 吴晶
 Xi'an 西安 City
 Xiao Yi'en 肖义恩
 Xie Jingyi 解静仪
 Xie Miaozi 解苗子
 Xu Zhongde 徐种德 (historical person); 许忠德
 (fictional character)
 Yangping 阳平 Pass
 Ye Guangqin 叶广芬
Yi Dai Xiao Xiong 一代枭雄
 Yong Ning Li 永宁里
 Zhang Dingwu 张定武
 Zhang Wanshu 张万树
 Zhong Yishan 钟一山
 Zhongde Shu Wu 种德书屋
 Zhu Cailing 朱彩铃
 Zhu Meiren 朱美人
Zhuangyuan Mei 状元媒